

The Media in India: An Analysis on Actors and Their Roles in Politics

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Abstract

Media holds a very significant role in liberal democratic regimes. Media actors influences the way social and political events are seen and evaluated. Free and plural media is the safeguard of a healthy democracy. Media has critical functions in a democratic regime. Journalism serves functions such as giving information , making investigation, and providing society a public forum. The main objective of this articles is to seek answers to the questions “how can the media profile and ownership in India be described” and “ what is the nature of the relationship between media and politics in India”. India has a developing media scene with thousands of outlets in multiple languages. Media in the country has been subjected to a structural change in recent years.

Keywords: Media in India, Media Freedom, Media Ownership.

Introduction

This articles aims to analyse media and politics relationship in India with a special emphasis on media structure , media actors, and media ownership with in the framework of the role of media in modern democratic regimes. Media actors play a major role in liberal democracies. Media discourses shapes the perceptions and preferences of the masses and the political elites generally use media as an instruments to influence the masses and gain consent to reproduce their dominant ideology.

This articles consists of three sections. The first section provides a theoretical framework about media- politics relationship. This section also includes a literature review on the topic. The second section addresses the Indian media profile in a general framework with actors in print and online media scene as well as radio. The third section will be the discussion part analyzing the role of media in Indian political life and also covering media ownership practices and the impact of these practices.

Media is seen as the “ fourth estate” in modern democracies besides the judiciary , executive, and legislative branches. It can be regarded as a watch dog for government roles such as giving information , making investment and analysis providing a basis for mobilization and education. Media freedom is therefore , vital for democracies.

India has powerful media organizations with thousands of outlets operating in different languages. Indian media has been active since the late 18th century . The print media started in India as early as 18th century . Indian media is seen as one of the oldest in the world .Media in India entered the period of privatization in the 1990s . It is known that there are no regulatory safeguards against political control over media actors in India.

Literature Review :

The Relationship between Media and Politics The ruling elites need media support in order to be able to hold effective public support and to be successful in the decision making process. The

press has been an indispensable part in establishing working democracies. The phenomenon of press freedom is a concept introduced as a vital prerequisite among democratic principles. In line to the economic and technological developments, the media has gained a more important dimension with the adoption of digital journalism. Thus, the “ press freedom “ today has more weight in democratic debates than it used to do in previous decades.

On other hand, the role of media in the political socialization process is important while media politics relationship. Acting as an independent political communication tool between different groups with a society , media contributes to the awareness of citizens especially in election times while contributing to their awareness in the case of abuse of power and political crisis as well.

The Media Profile in India

Indian media has been active since last 18th century . The print media started in India as early as 1780. In 1927 , radio broadcasting was launched in the country . Indian media is known as one of the oldest in the world based on 2019 data, there are around 900 private satellite TV stations and nearly the half of them are devoted to news coverage in India. In 2009, India was among the fourth largest television broadcast stations in the world with around 1400 stations. India has witnessed a huge media sector growth with the rise in the number of news TV channels as well as online and printed newspapers. As of 2018 there are more than 100000 registered publications in the country. India holds the second largest newspaper market in the world , with daily newspaper having a circulation of over 240 million copies as of 2018.

In terms of political orientations it can be said that the media of India is regarded as left leaning liberal ,especially the English languages media outlets. The main media actors in India are largely family owned . It is known that media ownership remains concentrated in the hands of the few in India. It is to be noted that the country currently hosts a growing tendency towards the cross media ownership where

the same content property in one sector is prompted through a different sector while audiences remain the same. According to a "Cross Media Ownership and Concentration in Indian Media" that was held

in 2017, it is stated that the cross media ownership has gained a new momentum with the privatization of more media sectors.

Graphic 1: Internet Users in India between 2015 and 2019

The Press Council of India is known as the actor responsible for the press regulation. It has the function of ensuring that the media in India is free. However it is very hard to keep the media free in Indian context as the big families own media outlets and compete in different business sectors as well.

The Role of Media in Indian Politics

I want this government to be criticized . Criticism makes democracy strong. Democracy cannot succeed without constructive criticism .These words were stated by the Indian prime Minister Narendra Modi in 2014. As Modi government faced with the rising crisis in the economy at home and increased tensions across the country , the Prime Minister took steps to weaken free media.

An important dimension related to the analysis of media freedoms in India today is the lack of an effective and independent regulatory regime. A significant point to emphasize while discussing media and politics relationship in India is the issues of advertising .In today media landscape in India , media actors are not only act as the intermediaries between the public opinion itself. The Hindu and National Herald newspapers have played an important role in the shaping as well as putting forth of the public opinion.

Conclusion

Media politics relationship is one of the main determinants showing the quality of the democratic governance in a country . A free and independent media is an indispensable actor in liberal democracies. It both presents information to the masses in a variety of issues from politics to economy and world affairs and it also functions as a watchdog , as an actor of surveillance over the activities of the government exercises upon media actors, the weaker the accountability and

transparency principles become in a political regime. Media and politics have always been in constant interaction and communication with one another. The medias function of reporting and monitoring should be kept away from political pressure. For this reason , a well-functioning regulatory regime along with institution and legal regulation must be established to protect media freedoms.

The main problem of the media in India is related with the media ownership structure. The use of advertising as a tool for reward and punishment by the political elites is the main factor that undermines media freedoms in India. The media ownership in India rests within the hands of a small group of elites who have certain political or financial affiliations and this paves the way for the weakening of democracy. The media actors cannot function freely in editorial and reporting process as they need profit making in order to survive.

The media sector in India is growing faster than the country 's economy, However it is not functioning as a watchdog to monitor elites and political affairs. It should be noted that not only India, but every country should adopt the goal of proving an appropriate ground for media actors to be able to make news and reporting in an open and free way based on editorial independence that serves the public interest.

References

1. Ardevol-Abreu, A(2015) , "Framing theory in communication research. Origins, development and current situation in Spain." Date of Accession: 30.12.2020 from http://www.revistalatinacs.org/070/paper/1053/RLC_S-paper_1053en.pdf.
2. Audit Bureau of Circulations," Daily newspapers Across Languages," Date of Accession: 30.12.2020

from

[http://www.auditbureau.org/files/JD%20Highest%20\(across%20languages\).pdf](http://www.auditbureau.org/files/JD%20Highest%20(across%20languages).pdf).

3. Basu, Arani (2014), "Understanding Media – Politics-Economy- Society Interrelationship in India: Relevance of Habermas and Chomsky." Date of

Accession:30.01.2021fromhttps://www.hu.berlin.de/transcience/Vol7_No2_27_35.pdf.

4. BBC(2019) ,India profile- Media “, 29.04.2019,Date of Accession : 30.12.2020 from <https://www.bbc.com/news/world/-south-asia-12557390>.

5. Bennett ,W,L.(1990) ,”Towards a theory of media- state Relations in the United States’, Journal of Communication ,40,pp.103-125.

6. Centre for the study of developing societies(2017),” Cross Media Ownership: Seminar Report “, 15.02.2017,Date of Accession: 30.12.2020 from <https://www.csds.in/sites/default/files/Seminar%20Report.pdf>

7. Curran, Jmes & Seaton, Jean (1992), Power without Responsibility: The Press and Broadcasting in Britain, London: Routledge.

8. The National Institute of Mass Communication, History of Mass Media in India”, Date of Accession: 30.12.2021 from <http://www.nimc-india.com/history-mass-media-india.html>.

9. Media Ownership Monitoring ,India, Radio News Monopoly”. Date of Accession 30.12.2020 from <https://india.mom-rsf.org/en/findings/radiomewsmonopoly/>.

10. SANNAM S4 ,”Digital and Social media Landscape in India,” Date of Accession : 30.12.2020from <https://sannamss4.com/digital-and-social-media-landscape-in-india/>

11. Withnall,Adam (2019),”How Modi Government Uses and spending to ‘Reward or Punish’ Indian media,”Independent, 20.07.2019, Date of Accession:03.01.2021 from <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/world/asia/india-a-modi-government-media-ad-spending-newspapers-press-freedom-a8990451.html>.